

From Mother Tongue Education to Multilingual Higher Education

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Abstract—Through the time, the higher education has changed the learning system since mother tongue to bilingual, and in this new century has been coming develop a multilingual education. All as part of globalization process of the countries and the education. Nevertheless, this change only has been effectively in countries of the first world, the rest have been lagging. Therefore, these countries require strengthen their higher education systems through models that give way to multilingual and bilingual education. In this way, shows a new model adapted from a systemic form to allow a higher bilingual and multilingual education in Latin America. This systematization aims to increase the skills and competencies student's, decrease the time learning of a second tongue, add to multilingualism in the American Latin Universities, also, contribute to position the region's countries in a better global status, and stimulate the development of new research in this area.

Keywords—Bilingual Education, Higher Education, Multilingual Education, Multilingual Education Model

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS research arise in the frame of project called Supply and Demand of higher education that Economics and Social Research Institute is developing, at the same, this research is from the interviews at the stage of qualitative research. Through history, from ancient times until today, the education has been a topic with high relevance in the world. The education has a common mission to guard, promote, update and transfer the culture of and between the people [1]. Furthermore, the globalization process that has been characterized the world along to the time, the development of science and society knowledge; allow the development of new demands in the higher education ambit. Every day, the organization demands professional with more capacities and that can be easy to adapt to any place in any region or country. Though, is necessary that the academy is fully integrate and closely related to the changes in world economies. In response, arise a considerable number of methodologies and proposals to pass from the mother tongue teaching to a bilingual teaching, and the most developed countries to a multilingual teaching.

Nevertheless, these changes, as a result of the globalization in the education and economies, only has been carried out successfully in the so-called first world countries, the rest of the countries has been lagging for many reasons.

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Nonetheless, today, the globalization accelerated process have brought migration movements in developing countries, transforming it in places that require have a higher bilingual education, and the best case, a higher multilingual education. All this, encourages that the education systems of these countries of Latin American to create fully multilingual educative systems [2].

The systematization of Latin American Higher Education has been difficult, and it hasn't be able in most of countries, according with the require need of the population, which move every day in a new employment market demands in different sceneries [3]. Therefore, the higher education of Latin American people require a restructuration of curricular design indexed and systematized in the second tongue learning, permitting pass from a mother tongue education to bilingual and in a close future to multilingual education [4]. For this, propose an adapted model to the curricular design that allow during the study time of the student, learn a second language, and a third one in an optative way.

This proposal comes to revolution the learning way in the American higher education systems and give the opportunity to form high competitive college professional and with the skill that fully globalization world require [5]. In this way, the research has developed in Latin American countries focusing in Honduras as place of the researchers.

In this meaning, introduce the aims of the research: 1. Implement a new model indexed to curricula which can incorporate a second language teaching. 2. Determinate the module number required for learning a second tongue during students training at the Latin American Universities. 3. Create curricula and curricular design to teach the multilingual educations modules.

II. METHODOLOGY / PROPOSAL

The time requires studying higher education in Latin American round of four to six years of study, time in which to apply methods for teaching a second language. This training time students can development two-year modular courses for students continuously receive teaching a second language [6].

Also, this model consist in brings classes at the same time with the other class that the students attends during the study period. Each complete period must be accompanied by a module of learning a second language. This activities will be take place within the first three years, until complete four module per year and twelve modules once finished of university career, time necessary for that students have learned and dominated of form verbal, oral, and writing other language.

During this time, the students has coursed, of intensive way, twelve modules, each module will have two hours duration. The foreign languages departments of each university should be responsible of the teaching system. Below is a graphical model.

Fig. 1 Represent the Systematization of the proposal model

Fig. 2 Represent the knowledge for year

Through studies, it is concluded that the academic curriculum best suited to multilingual education system is composed of at least 3 credits and 24 hours class, this will allow teachers to effectively teach the classes and students be efficient and effective in their learning. Therefore, the program academic curricular be composed as follows:

Compulsory Subject	E-learning	Lectures	Practicals	Hours	Credits	Pre requisite	Year
Module I	7	12	5	24	3		1
Module II	7	12	5	24	3	Module I	1
Module III	7	12	5	24	3	Module II	1
Module IV	7	12	5	24	3	Module III	1
Module V	8	9	7	24	3	Module IV	2
Module VI	8	9	7	24	3	Module V	2
Module VII	8	9	7	24	3	Module VI	2
Module VIII	8	9	7	24	3	Module VII	2
Module IX	7	8	9	24	4	Module VIII	3
Module X	7	8	9	24	4	Module IX	3
Module XI	7	5	12	24	4	Module X	3
Module XII	7	5	12	24	4	Module XI	3
Total Number of Credits Point from Obligatory Subjects							40

Fig. 3 Proposed Program Study

The UNAH has a unit responsible to teach Foreign Languages, which will be the entity responsible of coordinate the proposal in this investigation. For this, used all his teachers and undergraduate students for they do their professional practice university, imparting the classes of modules of years 1 and 2.

Nevertheless, at the start of the third year, the modules will be taught by expert's teachers, in order to provide reliability and rigor to the process.

At the same time, the faculties of the University shall provide full elective classes in English, this for students that are adopted language from different perspectives. To do this, from research of analysis skills of teachers of the Faculty of Economics of the UNAH, been taken to fully bilingual teachers, to teach their subjects incorporated entirely in English. This process will allow the student to consolidate their knowledge and strengthen their bilingualism.

According to research data, the unit more consolidated and would be the first to participate, will be the Faculty of Economics, was considered to 363 teachers, a total of 19.467 students, at a rate of 53 students per teacher. In this way, we try to find methodologies to provide a quality education that give way to competitive students. Therefore, we intend to specialize and update knowledge in a foreign language of the teachers, focused, that these professors can be teach subjects in another language. This case only applies to teachers who are highly trained and proficient in English as a second language. The process will be to classify bilingual teachers, train them in teaching a mother tongue, moving the academic curriculum of these subjects in English, and finally, teach subjects in English to students. This will come to consolidate the knowledge acquired by the student and give validity to the process of bilingualism applied by the higher education institution.

Fig. 4 Teacher Selection Process

After three years, the model leads to multilingualism, space where the students, before to have all requirements, can learn another language that prefers. These modules will consist of two years of study, enabling students to complete their higher education studies being bilingual, and the best of case, multilingual. The validity and reliability of the system will give the application of international tests for the assessment of language skills, such as the TOEFL, DALF, DELF, DAAD language certificate, JLPT, among others. Be represented graphically.

Fig. 5 Represent the second level of multilingual education

Fig. 6 Represent the knowledge for the next two year

III. CONCLUSION

Latin American requires of the implementation of models to improve the quality of higher education, in this way, offer a model that the student pass a process of mother tongue learning to multilingual education, would give final product more competitive and globally accepted in the employment market.

Students entering in the process will be able to apply any test of language skills and adopt them with success. Providing reliability to the learning a second language model.

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